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Classification of Korean rice germplasm based on isozyme polymorphism

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Isozymes are important biochemical markers in genetic and plant breeding research. Isozyme polymorphism has provided useful information for classifying rice cultivars, thus enabling breeders to transfer desirable traits through hybridization within and between groups.

We analyzed traditional and modern rice cultivars from Korea using gel electrophoresis. Five isozyme loci (*Pgi1*, *Pgi2*, *Amp1*, *Amp2*, *Amp3*) were studied following the classification scheme of Glaszmann (1987). Zymograms were revealed following the staining procedure of Glaszmann et al (1988).

Of the 286 cultivars, 42 (14.7%) belonged to group 1 (indica types). This is the result of hybridization between indica and japonica types cultivated during 1976-80 as "Tongil type" in Korea. Most (242, or 84.6%) were classified as group VI (japonica types), which are currently heavily cultivated in Korea. Only two varieties were mixed. ■

Heritability and genetic correlation for component characters of yield sink capacity in rice

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Yield sink capacity (YSC), the maximum size of sink organs to be harvested per rice plant is a product of the number of grains plant⁻¹ (= number of panicles plant⁻¹ [NP] ×

Genetic correlation and realized heritability for traits related to yield sink capacity of rice.*

Trait ^b	YSC	NP	NG	NPB	NGPB	NSB	NGSB	GL	GW
NP	-0.449	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NG	0.748	-0.690	<u>0.200</u>	0.959	*0.281	*0.544	*0.130	-0.256	0.472
NPB	0.041	-0.467	0.342	<u>0.426</u>	*0.507	-0.108	-0.122	-0.155	0.515
NGPB	0.435	-0.347	0.687	0.504	<u>0.040</u>	-0.787	-0.187	0.136	0.470
NSB	0.636	-0.286	0.642	-0.495	0.168	<u>0.179</u>	*0.368	-0.103	*0.319
NGSB	0.720	-0.294	0.619	-0.454	0.231	0.917	<u>0.129</u>	0.124	-0.074
GL	0.246	0.030	-0.313	-0.319	-0.181	-0.050	0.113	<u>0.270</u>	*0.153
GW	0.267	-0.559	0.147	0.268	-0.178	-0.047	-0.022	0.052	<u>0.773</u>
RGP	-0.964	-0.046	-0.384	0.899	-0.180	-1.008	-1.184	-0.393	-0.028

*Above the diagonal (underlined): genetic correlation coefficients estimated from selection responses in F₂ and F₃ populations of Nakateshinsenbon/Hieri. * = Sign of coefficient could not be determined. The data for YSC, NP, and RGP were not available. Below the diagonal: genetic correlation coefficients estimated from variance and covariance components in recombinant inbreds of Koshihikari/Nakateshinsenbon. Diagonal (underlined): realized heritabilities estimated from selection responses in F₂ and F₃ populations of Nakateshinsenbon/Hieri. *See text for the meanings of the abbreviations.

number of grains panicle⁻¹ [NG]) multiplied by single grain weight. Grain ripening ability, measured as the ripened grain percentage (RGP), is generally superior for grains on primary branches compared with that for secondary branches. Therefore NG must be broken into components: number of primary branches panicle⁻¹ (NPB), number of grains on primary branches primary branch⁻¹ (NGPB), number of secondary branches primary branch⁻¹ (NSB), and number of grains on secondary branches secondary branch⁻¹ (NGSB).

We estimated genetic correlation (rg) for these YSC components using two experiments. In experiment I, genetic correlation was estimated from variance and covariance components in 49 recombinant inbred lines of Koshihikari/Nakateshinsenbon cultivated under four environments. In experiment II, rg was estimated from direct and correlated responses in selecting F₂ and F₃ populations (Falconer 1989) of Nakateshinsenbon/Hieri. Realized heritability was also estimated.

In experiment I, YSC was positively correlated with NG ($r = 0.748$), but not with grain length (GL) or grain width (GW). A high negative correlation was detected between YSC and RGP ($r = -0.964$), perhaps due to the negative correlations between RGP and NSB ($r = -1.008$) and RGP and NGSB ($r = -1.184$). In contrast, NPB was positively and tightly correlated with RGP ($r = 0.899$). In experiment II, NPB showed a high positive correlation with NG ($r = 0.959$) and the highest realized heritability among the NG components.

In addition, NPB was not positively correlated with NSB and NGSB in either experiment.

These results suggest a strategy for developing a promising panicle type that realizes both high NG and RGP that consists of increasing the NPB to provide numerous well-ripened grains and suppressing the NSB and/or NGSB to not overproduce unfilled grains.

Chau and Bhargava (1993) demonstrated that the large sink sizes of high-yielding indica cultivars were mainly due to high NPB and high NPB × NGPB. The genetic nature of NPB must be understood more precisely.

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Heading-time genes control photoperiod insensitivity of rice cultivar Norin 20

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Rice cultivars grown in Hokkaido, the highest latitude area (41-44 °N) in Japan, flower far earlier than any other Japanese cultivars. Previous work on geographical analysis for heading traits revealed that the

extreme earliness of Hokkaido cultivars depends on extremely weak photoperiod sensitivity.

We analyzed the genetic factors controlling the weak photoperiod sensitivity of Hokkaido cultivars by comparing the gene constitution and degree of photoperiod sensitivity of photoperiod-insensitive Norin 20 with those of several other cultivars.

A scatter diagram was constructed for 26 Hokkaido varieties according to basic vegetative growth (BVG) and photoperiod sensitivity (PS) (see figure). BVG was expressed as days to heading under short daylength (10 h) condition, and PS was expressed as the difference between days to heading under whole daylength minus days to heading under short daylength. The cultivars could easily be classified into three groups based on PS: group I (PS < 3.0), group II (4.0 < PS < 10.0), and group III (PS > 20.0). The PS of Norin 20 was 0.6, confirming that this variety has completely lost photoperiod sensitivity (Vergara and Chang 1985).

We compared the gene constitution between Norin 20 (group I) and varieties randomly chosen from groups II and III. Seven varieties were crossed with 10 tester lines to study four photoperiod sensitivity loci: E_1 , E_2 , E_3 , and $Se1$. The dominant alleles of E_1 and $Se1$ loci (E_1 and $Se1^a$ ($Se1^a$)) remarkably improved the photoperiod sensitivity of rice (Okumoto et al 1991), but the effects of those of E_2 and E_3 loci are small (Yamagata et al 1986). (See table for the results of the gene analysis.) For the E_1 locus, all of the varieties examined carry e_1 , an allele for photoperiod

Estimated genotypes for heading-time loci E_1 , E_2 , E_3 , and $Se1$ and degree of photoperiod sensitivity* of seven Hokkaido varieties.

Hokkaido variety	Genotype ^b				Photoperiod sensitivity
	E_1	E_2	E_3	$Se1$	
Norin 20	e_1e_1	e_2e_2	e_3e_3	$Se1^cSe1^c$	0.6
Kitahikari	e_1e_1	e_2e_2	e_3e_3	$Se1^cSe1^c$	6.8
Yukara	e_1e_1	e_2e_2	e_3e_3	$Se1^aSe1^a$	21.0
Kirara 397	e_1e_1	E_2E_2	e_3e_3	$Se1^aSe1^a$	8.0
Shlokari	e_1e_1	e_2e_2	E_3E_3	$Se1^aSe1^a$	5.3
Elko	e_1e_1	e_2e_2	e_3e_3	$Se1^aSe1^a$	23.3
Sasahonami	e_1e_1	E_2E_2	E_3E_3	$Se1^aSe1^a$	5.3

*See Fig. 1. ^b E_1 , E_2 , E_3 , and $Se1^a$ = photoperiod-sensitive alleles. e_1 , e_2 , e_3 , and $Se1^c$ = photoperiod-insensitive alleles.

Scatter diagram of 26 Hokkaido varieties according to basic vegetative growth and photoperiod sensitivity.

*Days to heading under whole-day length - (days to heading under short-day length [10 h]). ^bDays to heading under short-day length (10 h).

insensitivity. No alleles for photoperiod sensitivity were found among the varieties for the other loci. Norin 20 carries alleles for photoperiod insensitivity alleles at all the above loci, and its genotype was estimated to be $e_1e_1 e_2e_2 e_3e_3 Se1^cSe1^c$. This suggests that the photoperiod insensitivity of Norin 20 can be attributed to the combining effect of these four alleles. However, the cultivars of the same genotype for four loci existed even in Groups II (Kitahikari, PS = 6.8) and III (Yukara, PS = 21.0).

We conclude that e_1 is an essential gene for cultivating rice in Hokkaido. The combining effect of e_1 with an allele(s) for photoperiod insensitivity—but not at E_2 , E_3 , and $Se1$ loci—controls the weak photoperiod sensitivity of Hokkaido varieties.

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QTL analysis of rice seedling vigor in japonica and indica genetic backgrounds

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Breeding for enhanced seedling vigor—a plant's ability to emerge rapidly from soil or water (Heydecker 1960)—continues to be a major challenge for rice breeders in both tropical (Herdt 1991) and temperate (McKenzie et al 1994) rice-growing countries. Vigorous varieties are needed for optimum stand establishment under direct seeded rice cultures. The development of molecular marker maps in rice (McCouch et al 1988) makes it possible to identify and locate genetic factors or quantitative trait loci (QTLs) controlling polygenic characters.

Rice seedling vigor is associated with shoot and root lengths under water-seeded rice culture (Jones and Peterson 1976) and coleoptile and mesocotyl lengths under drill seeding (Turner et al 1982). To identify and locate QTLs underlying these characters, two high-vigor cultivars, indica Black Gora (BG) and temperate japonica Italica Livorno (IL), were crossed to the same maternal parent, Labelle (LBL), a low-vigor tropical japonica. Two molecular maps were constructed based on 204 F_2 plants and 117 restriction fragment length polymorphisms (RFLPs) in LBL/BG and on 118 F_2 plants and 129 random amplified polymorphic DNAs (RAPDs) and 18 RFLPs in LBL/IL.

The LBL/BG map spanned 1496 Haldane cM, with an average marker spacing of 14 cM. Linkage analysis was performed using Mapmaker 3.0 (Lander et al 1987). Total length of the LL/IL map was